

SAN MARTIN DE PORRES UNIVERSITY - NORTH SUBSIDIARY

HUMAN MEDICINE PROGRAM

QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire about Medicinal Plants

Date:

Answer each question based on your experience with the use of medicinal plants.

I. Sociodemographic data

- 1. Location:
- 2. Age:
- 3. Gender: M () F ()

II. Information on medicinal plants

- 4. Have you ever used medicinal plants to treat diseases? Yes () Not ()
- 5. Has your family been cured with medicinal plants? Yes () Not ()
- 6. Do you buy plants? Yes () Not ()
- 7. Do you frequently use medicinal plants? Yes () Not ()
- 8. When they get sick, who do they go to first?
They self-medicate with medicinal plants ()
Healer ()
- 9. In extreme cases, do they go to the medical post? Yes () Not ()
- 10. Who taught them the use of medicinal plants?
Parents and grandparents ()
Healer ()
Others ()
- 11. Does it transmit the knowledge of medicinal plants? Yes () Not ()
- 12. How do they acquire medicinal plants?
From field ()
From city ()
- 13. In your community, are there medicinal plants?
In Abundant ()
Scarce ()
- 14. For what illness have you used medicinal plants?
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15. What parts of the plant do you use?

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16. How do you prepare the part of the plant used?

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17. How many times a day do you administer the plant preparation?

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18. How many doses per day does the treatment indicate?

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19. How long is the treatment in days?

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